

Astrobiologi Poster Projekt til nationale rumkonference 2023 på SDU

Art:	Citizen Science / STEAM communication
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Tid:	n/a
Antal elever:	5
GDPR / pictures for public?	Yes. Permission obtained.
Lærerkontakt:	n/a
Formidler / supervisor:	Tobias C. Hinse (Syddansk Universitet, FKF / SDU-Galaxy).
Information:	I supervised a group of SDU biology students to create a review poster within the field of astrobiology. This resulted in 5/8 students participating in the danish national youth space conference and national space conference on various topics relating space science with biology. Posters are part of science communication and some of them are uploaded to zenodo.

Missing from the group pictures is Jaspur Ellingsgaard (Poster title: "Iron reduction as a viable metabolic pathway in Enceladus' ocean (Roche et al. 2023)").

“Iron reduction as a viable metabolic pathway in Enceladus’ ocean” (Roche *et al.* 2023)

A review. Can we detect microbial-biological activity on Saturn’s moon Enceladus?
By Jaspur Ellingsgaard, Biologisk Institut, SDU.

The Cassini mission (1997 - 2017) which explored Saturn and its moons discovered evidence of a subsurface ocean below the ice sheet covering the moon Enceladus. It is believed that hydrothermal vents exist on the bottom which could provide potential microorganisms with nutrients and iron-rich minerals.

“[...] this work has added additional support for Enceladus as an astrobiological target in future missions, missions which could aim to detect iron in Enceladus’ plumes [...]” (Roche *et al.*, 2023).

Take-Home Message - A vent driven supply of Acetate and H₂ could sustain iron reducing bacteria under Enceladus’ subsurface ocean conditions. In spite of *Geobacter sulphureducens* being a poor candidate for this type research it nonetheless survived and grew under the simulated extraterrestrial environment of Enceladus. Future studies should focus on finding an alkaliphilic, and halophilic species better suited for the Enceladus environment.

A special thank you to NovoNordisk Fonden who funded this project. Thank to SDU and Poul Erik Larsen. Consideration for the growing up-and-coming scientists an opportunity to use their health in publications.

Roche, M., Fox-Powell, M., Hamp, R., & Byrne, J. (2023). Iron reduction as a viable metabolic pathway in Enceladus’ ocean. *International Journal of Astrobiology*, 22(5), 539-558.

Background Image Credit: NASA/JPL-Caltech